

Settlement of Competition Disputes before the Fair Competition Commission: An Alternative Dispute Resolution Perspective

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Abstract:

This study examines how disputes are settled within the Fair Competition Commission (FCC) of Tanzania, utilizing alternative dispute resolution (ADR) as a form of dispute resolution. It reviews the procedures under the Fair Competition Commission Rules, which allow parties to request a settlement after the Commission issues its provisional findings and before a final decision is made. Data for this study were collected through documentary review and supplemented by interviews with key stakeholders, including FCC officials, legal practitioners, and business representatives. The collected data were analyzed using thematic content analysis and principles of statutory interpretation. The findings reveal that while ADR is recognized within the FCC framework, its discretionary nature, lack of procedural clarity, and limited application undermine its effectiveness as an alternative to formal adjudication. Settlement is rarely used, and the absence of published outcomes or official reports raises concerns regarding transparency and stakeholder confidence. The study recommends amending existing laws and developing clear ADR guidelines to make settlement processes more predictable, transparent, and effective in the enforcement of competition law.

Keywords: Fair Competition Commission, Alternative Dispute Resolution, Disputes, Settlement Procedures, Tanzania.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Competition is both a legal and economic concept that describes how firms strive to secure a larger share of the market for selling or buying goods and services. In pursuing this advantage, some businesses resort to practices that distort fair market operations and harm consumers. Common examples include price fixing, unlawful mergers, abuse of market dominance, and cartel arrangements, all prohibited under competition law. To prevent such conduct, Tanzania established the Fair Competition Commission (FCC) to investigate and address unfair market conduct. Operating under an inquisitorial framework, the FCC may detect a violation, initiate a complaint, conduct investigations, hold hearings, and issue determinations. Yet in certain circumstances, a party under investigation may seek a settlement. The Fair Competition Act¹ and the Fair Competition Commission Rules² provide a pathway for negotiated settlement or compliance agreements instead of proceeding to a full formal hearing.

This possibility raises an important question: do these settlements qualify as genuine Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR), or are they simply administrative enforcement measures presented differently? ADR generally involves party autonomy, neutrality, confidentiality, and flexibility, enabling disputes to be resolved outside formal courtroom procedures. These features inspired this study to examine whether the FCC's settlement process truly reflects the core principles of ADR. The discussion analyses the legal and institutional framework of Tanzania's competition regime and explores the key challenges and future prospects for strengthening ADR within the FCC's enforcement process.

2. THE EVOLUTION OF COMPETITION LAW

The growth of competition law in Tanzania reflects the country's wider economic changes and the policies that shaped them. After Tanganyika, now Tanzania Mainland, gained independence in 1961, most of the legal and economic structures were inherited from the colonial period.³ At that time the economy was small and underdeveloped. The government maintained a light hand on economic activities, which were largely controlled by a small foreign-owned private sector.⁴ Many key businesses operated as monopolies and were often managed from outside the country, especially from Nairobi, Kenya⁵. This

¹ The Fair Competition Act [Cap 285 R.E 2023].

² Rule 19 to 21 of The Fair Competition Rules. GN 344 27/07/2018.

³ Noor Kassum (2007) *Tanzanian, Nyerere Loyalist And Ismaili Africa's Winds of Change: Memoirs of an International Tanzanian*. https://www.researchgate.net/journal/The-Journal-of-African-History-1469-5138?_tp=eyJjb250ZXhoIjp7ImZpcnNoUGFnZSI6InB1YmxpY2FoaW9uIiwicGFnZSI6InB1YmxpY2FoaW9uIn19. Accessed on 20 September 2025.

⁴ Goodluck Temu (2014), 'Reflections on the Enforcement of Competition Rules in Tanzania', *Eastern Africa Law Review*, Volume 41(2), pp 86-124.

⁵ Sylvia Chifungo (2022), *An Examination on the Role of Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority (EWURA) in the Implementation of Consumer Protection in Tanzania*. Journal of Legal Studies & Research. The Law Brigade Publisher. Accessed on 20 September 2025.

approach lasted until 1967 when the ruling party, Tanganyika African National Union (TANU), announced the Arusha Declaration. The declaration set out a plan for a socialist and self-reliant economy. The government took control of major areas of production and trade, quickly nationalizing many enterprises and creating state trading corporations that operated as government monopolies.⁶

To manage pricing in this new economic framework, the government enacted the Regulation of Prices Act,⁷ which established the Price Commission. This body was responsible for setting the prices of essential goods and services, removing such determinations from the forces of supply and demand. However, the centrally planned economy began to lose momentum by the mid-1980s, largely due to internal economic pressures and global political shifts, especially the collapse of the Soviet Union and its restructuring policies under Gorbachev.⁸ Tanzania began to liberalize and move toward a market-driven economy, which created the need for a competition law to prevent abuse of market power. Parliament expressed concern about consumer protection in a liberalized market without state-controlled pricing. At the same time, the Presidential Parastatal Sector Reform Commission, established under the Public Corporation Act⁹, started privatizing more than 400 state-run enterprises.¹⁰ These included major utilities and infrastructure providers such as the Tanzania Railway Corporation, Tanzania Electric Supply Company (TANESCO), Tanzania Petroleum Development Corporation (TPDC), and Dar es Salaam Water and Sewerage Corporation (DAWASCO). Because these sectors tend toward monopoly, they require oversight even as they move into private hands.¹¹

The first attempt to regulate competition came with the Fair-Trade Practices Act. Although it provided a legal basis for monitoring market behaviour, it soon showed serious weaknesses. The law placed the Office of the Trade Practices Commissioner within the Ministry of Trade, meaning it was not independent¹². A proposed Trade Practices Tribunal under the law was never set up, and the Commissioner's role was only advisory, with final decisions left to the Minister. The law also combined competition oversight with

⁶ Michael Chugozie Anyaehie (2013). Appraisal of African Identity for Sustainable Development. <https://www.scirp.org/journal/home?journalid=741>. Accessed on 10 September 2025.

⁷ [Act No. 19 of 1973].

⁸ Goodluck Temu (2014), 'Reflections on the Enforcement of Competition Rules in Tanzania', *Eastern Africa Law Review*, Volume 41(2), pp 86-124.

⁹ Act of 1992.

¹⁰ Mushtaq Luqmani (2011). Privatizing state-owned enterprises: A model for developing countries. *International Journal of Commerce and Management* 21(3):256-272. https://www.researchgate.net/journal/International-Journal-of-Commerce-and-Management-1056-9219?_tp=eyJjb250ZXhoIjp7ImZpcnNoUGFnZSI6InB1YmxpY2FoaW9uIiwicGFnZSI6InB1YmxpY2FoaW9uIn19. Accessed on 1 July 2025.

¹¹ Goodluck Temu (2014), *Op Cit.*

¹² Goodluck Temu (2014), *Op Cit.*

economic regulation, two areas that work in very different ways¹³. Competition law relies on market forces to prevent price fixing, while regulation often involves setting prices and service standards. Combining the two created confusion and conflict. The Act also failed to define anti-competitive conduct clearly, which made enforcement difficult and left consumers unprotected.¹⁴

These problems led to the repeal of the 1994 Act and the introduction of the Fair Competition Act of 2003,¹⁵ which followed international best practices and the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) Model Law. The new law, which took effect in 2004, established the Fair Competition Commission (FCC) as an independent body responsible for both competition and consumer protection. The Commission was given legal personality and operational independence, including protection from civil liability for actions taken in good faith.¹⁶ It has broad powers to investigate and prosecute anti-competitive conduct such as price fixing, bid rigging, abuse of dominance, and cartel arrangements. The Commission can act on complaints or on its own initiative, conduct investigations, hear cases and issue binding decisions with remedies and penalties. It also carries out advocacy, raises consumer awareness and contributes to policy and legal reforms, allowing it to cover the entire process from receiving a complaint to final determination.¹⁷

Even with this strong mandate, an important question remains about how the Commission resolves competition disputes. The law allows for settlements and compliance agreements as alternatives to full hearings. Under Rule 19 (6) and 21 of the Fair Competition Rules¹⁸ a respondent may propose a settlement by admitting liability and suggesting appropriate remedies. The Commission then evaluates whether the proposal is adequate and lawful, and the Act places no limits on which contraventions can be settled. The respondent may present written or oral submissions in reply to the Commission's provisional findings, while other parties, such as formal complainants, are also permitted to submit their views in accordance with Rule 20(6).¹⁹ If new evidence

¹³ Mlyambina, Y.J 2021. Concurrent Jurisdiction in Competition Law Enforcement in Tanzania with Some Lessons from The United Kingdom and South Africa. Accessed in September 2025.

¹⁴ Ibid.

¹⁵ [Cap 285 RE 2023].

¹⁶ Section 62 of Fair Competition Act R.E 2023. State that; *There is hereby established a Commission to be known as the Fair Competition Commission. (2) The Commission shall be independent and shall perform its functions and exercise its powers independently and impartially without fear or favour.*

¹⁷ Goodluck Temu (2014), 'Reflections on the Enforcement of Competition Rules in Tanzania', Eastern Africa Law Review, Volume 41(2), pp 86-124.

¹⁸ [GN No. 344 of 2018].

¹⁹ Ibid. 20(6) provides that; *Formal complainants and third parties who may be able to materially assist the assessment of the case shall have a right to submit written representations in the manner prescribed under the Rules.*

comes to light, Rule 20²⁰ requires the Commission to issue supplementary provisional findings and gives the respondent fourteen days to respond. These provisions create a structured settlement process, but whether this process truly embodies the principles of Alternative Dispute Resolution remains the central issue of this study. The next section presents the conceptual framework, outlining the key concepts necessary to understand this research.

3. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This part conceptualises and clarifies the key terms and concepts as used in this study to ensure conceptual clarity and consistency.

3.1 Competition and competition law

Competition has both economic and legal meanings depending on the context. Economically, it refers to the rivalry among businesses as they strive to attract customers by offering better products, lower prices, or innovative services²¹. This rivalry is essential for the healthy functioning of a market economy because it pushes firms to operate efficiently, reduce production costs, improve quality, and embrace new technologies. These dynamics benefit consumers through lower prices, more choices, and better goods and services, while also driving overall economic growth and development²². Legally, competition is viewed as a market condition that prevents excessive concentration of economic power. It ensures that no single business or group of businesses can dominate prices, control supply, or impose unfair terms on consumers and competitors. Without competition, monopolistic or collusive practices can emerge, leading to inflated prices, reduced consumer choice, and market inefficiencies.²³

To guard against such outcomes, governments around the world have enacted competition laws, sometimes called antitrust laws, to preserve and protect fair rivalry in the marketplace. These laws prohibit activities that distort or eliminate competition, such as cartels, price fixing, and abuse of market dominance, and they regulate mergers and acquisitions that may weaken competition. Their aim is not only to punish anti-competitive behaviour but also to encourage innovation, protect consumers, and promote a level playing field for all market participants.²⁴

²⁰ Ibid.

²¹ Korah, V., & O'Sullivan, D. (2010). *Competition law of the EC and UK* (6th ed.). Oxford University Press.

²² Bellamy et al., 2011. Competitive Advantage Definition with Types and Examples. https://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/competitive_advantage.asp. Accessed on 1 June 2025.

²³ This has been referred to as a hands-on approach to the economy. See Laitaika, E, "Legal and Institutional Aspects of Fair Competition in Tanzania," Volume 5 Open University Law Journal, 2014, p. 59

²⁴ Mohammad Shahjahan Siddiqui, (2023). Defining the importance and challenges of market competition Daffodil International University. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/366846854_Defining_the_importance_and_challenges_of_market_competition. Accessed on 1 May 2025.

3.2 Anti-competitive practices

Anti-competitive practices refer to conduct by enterprises that hinders, restricts, or distorts competition in a market. Such conduct interferes with the competitive process, often resulting in consumer harm, reduced market efficiency, and the exclusion of rivals²⁵. These practices may occur through collusive agreements, unfair use of market power, or structural arrangements that limit competition. Under the Fair Competition Act,²⁶ particularly Sections 8 to 11,²⁷ various forms of anti-competitive behaviour are prohibited. These include restrictive agreements (such as cartels), abuse of dominant position, and mergers or acquisitions that substantially lessen competition. It is important to note that dominance in itself is not unlawful. A firm may gain a dominant position in the market through innovation, efficiency, or competitive conduct. However, it is the abuse of that dominant position that constitutes an anti-competitive practice.²⁸

Abuse of dominance can occur in several ways. A typical example is where a dominant firm engages in predatory pricing, by deliberately setting prices below cost with the intention of driving competitors out of the market, only to raise prices later once competition has been eliminated²⁹. Other forms of abuse include refusing to supply essential inputs to downstream competitors, engaging in exclusive dealing arrangements that block market access, or applying dissimilar conditions to equivalent transactions, thereby placing some trading parties at a competitive disadvantage.³⁰ This was also held in the Case of *Tanzania Cigarette Company Ltd v. Fair Competition Commission*,³¹ the dispute arose from FCC's investigation into alleged anti-competitive practices by the Tanzania Cigarette Company (TCC), which was accused of abusing its dominant market position through restrictive trade practices. TCC challenged the FCC's investigative and enforcement procedures before the High Court (Commercial Division), arguing that the Commission had exceeded its statutory mandate and had not adhered to principles of fairness and due process in handling the matter.

The case reflects the broader tension between regulatory authority and corporate rights, as companies often turn to the courts to review or overturn FCC decisions they perceive

²⁵ Ibid.

²⁶ [Cap 285 RE 2023], Section 8(1) provides that; *A person shall not make or give effect to an agreement if the object, effect or likely effect of the agreement is to appreciably prevent, restrict or distort competition.*

²⁷ Ibid.

²⁸ See OECD Competition Trend, 2020 at <http://www.oecd.org/competition/oecdcompetition-trends.htm>. Accessed in 20 September 2025.

²⁹ Goodluck Temu (2014), 'Reflections on the Enforcement of Competition Rules in Tanzania', *Eastern Africa Law Review*, Volume 41(2), pp 86-124.

³⁰ Noor Kassum (2007) *Tanzanian, Nyerere Loyalist and Ismaili Africa's Winds of Change. Op Cit.*

³¹ Misc. Commercial Cause No. 46 of 2012 (HC Commercial Division).

as arbitrary or procedurally flawed. Its significance lies in highlighting the lack of clarity and predictability in FCC's processes, which in turn raises questions about whether ADR mechanisms, if properly legislated and procedurally safeguarded, could provide a more balanced, efficient, and trusted avenue for resolving such disputes. The case illustrates that without clear ADR frameworks, businesses are more likely to resort to litigation, thereby undermining the efficiency and flexibility that ADR is intended to promote in competition law enforcement.

4. REGULATORY FRAMEWORK FOR COMPETITION

The legal and regulatory framework governing competition in Tanzania contains various laws and institutions vested with the authority to promote and protect effective competition, prevent anti-competitive conduct, and safeguard consumer welfare. This framework establishes both substantive rules of conduct and the institutional mechanisms for enforcement and dispute resolution.

The Constitution of the United Republic of Tanzania, 1977, stands as the supreme law from which all other legislation derives its validity. Articles 11, 14, and 18³² recognize the rights of citizens, who are also consumers, to access necessities and to enjoy protection against violations of their rights. Article 30(3)³³ guarantees every person the right to seek redress before a competent court where such rights are infringed or threatened. Furthermore, Article 107A (2) (d)³⁴ supports the use of Alternative Dispute Resolution, promoting efficient and amicable settlement of market and consumer disputes. These constitutional provisions collectively anchor the protection of consumer rights and the promotion of fair competition.

The Fair Competition Act³⁵ is the principal statute for regulating market conduct and ensuring consumer protection. It aims to promote and protect effective competition in trade and commerce, prevent unfair and misleading market practices, foster innovation and efficient allocation of resources, and safeguard consumer interests. The Act prohibits anti-competitive agreements under section 8(1),³⁶ including practices that distort or restrict competition. Section 9 specifically outlaws' horizontal restrictive practices such as price-fixing, collective boycotts, and collusive tendering. Agreements outside section

³² Constitution of the United Republic of Tanzania 1977.

³³ Ibid. Article 30(3) narrated that; *Any person claiming that any provision in this Part of this Chapter or in any law concerning his right or duty owed to him has been, is being or is likely to be violated by any person anywhere in the United Republic, may institute proceedings for redress in the High Court.*

³⁴ Ibid. Article 107A(2)(d), states that; *In delivering decisions in matters of civil and criminal matters in accordance with the laws, the court shall observe the following principles, that is to say; to promote and enhance dispute resolution among persons involved in the disputes.*

³⁵ [Cap 285 RE 2023],

³⁶ Ibid.

9³⁷ are evaluated using the rule of reason, where pro-competitive benefits are weighed against potential harm. The Act also provides for Fair Competition Rules, which guide procedural aspects of investigations, hearings, and settlements. For example, the Rules outline how parties may respond to provisional findings and propose settlements, ensuring that enforcement remains transparent and consistent with principles of natural justice, Rule 19, FCC Rules of 2018.³⁸

Administration and enforcement of competition law in Tanzania rest primarily with the Fair Competition Commission and the Fair Competition Tribunal, alongside other sector regulators. The Commission is an independent government agency charged with implementing the Act.³⁹ It investigates anti-competitive practices, enforces compliance, and protects consumers from unfair or misleading conduct. The Commission also applies the Fair Competition Rules, manages settlement procedures, and issues directives necessary for effective market regulation. Although the FCC is established to safeguard competition in the country, the law also establishes other regulators to deal with competition in specific areas and gives them concurrent jurisdiction with the FCC. The FCC has no power to intervene in these sectors but may issue advice and advocacy on the enforcement of competition. These regulators include the Energy and Water Utilities Regulatory Authority (EWURA), the Tanzania Communications Regulatory Authority (TCRA), the Land Transport Regulatory Authority (LATRA), and the Tanzania Civil Aviation Authority (TCAA). These authorities operate under their respective enabling statutes: the EWURA Act, the TCRA Act, the LATRA Act, and the Civil Aviation Act. These laws assign regulatory functions over their respective sectors, including responsibilities directly related to the monitoring and control of anti-competitive conduct.

The Fair Competition Tribunal, established under section 83(1) of the Act⁴⁰ is a quasi-judicial body comprising a High Court Judge as Chairperson and six other members appointed by the President in consultation with the Attorney-General. It exercises appellate jurisdiction over Commission decisions and those of other regulatory bodies such as the Water Utilities Regulatory Authority (EWURA), the Tanzania Civil Aviation Authority (TCAA), the Land Transport Regulatory Authority (LATRA), and the Tanzania Communications Regulatory Authority (TCRA). Guided by the principles of natural justice, the Tribunal ensures fairness and equity in resolving competition disputes. These institutions, supported by constitutional guarantees and the detailed provisions of the Fair Competition Act and its Rules, collectively form the backbone of Tanzania's legal and

³⁷ Fair Competition Act Cap 285 RE 2023. Which provides for; *Prohibition of certain agreements irrespective of their effect on competition*

³⁸ [GN No. 344 of 2018],

³⁹ Fair Competition Act Cap 285 RE 2023.

⁴⁰ Ibid.

regulatory framework for competition. The next section presents the conceptual framework, which outlines the key concepts and analytical foundations necessary for understanding this study.

5. ALTERNATIVE DISPUTE RESOLUTION (ADR)

ADR refers to various mechanisms used to resolve disputes without resorting to formal court proceedings. These include arbitration, mediation, conciliation, negotiation, and other collaborative approaches aimed at reaching a mutually acceptable solution⁴¹. ADR is grounded in the idea that disputes can often be resolved more effectively, efficiently, and amicably outside the adversarial structure of traditional litigation. It emphasizes party autonomy, confidentiality, flexibility in procedures, and cost-effectiveness, making it particularly suitable in commercial, civil, and administrative matters.⁴²

Several scholars have explored the concept of ADR and offered distinct definitions. According to Henry J. Brown and Arthur L. Marriott, ADR refers to “a range of procedures that serve as alternatives to litigation for the resolution of disputes, generally involving the intercession and assistance of a neutral third party.” They emphasize the role of impartial facilitators in helping parties resolve their conflicts outside the formal court system⁴³. On the other hand, Gary B. Born defines ADR more broadly, stating that it encompasses “any method of dispute resolution other than litigation, including arbitration, mediation, conciliation, and early neutral evaluation.⁴⁴ These definitions reveal the diversity and scope of ADR mechanisms and highlight their increasing importance in both domestic and international legal contexts.

The rise of ADR is closely tied to its numerous advantages. First, it is generally faster and less costly than litigation, helping parties save time and resources. Second, it promotes confidentiality, which is particularly valuable in commercial disputes where sensitive information may be at stake.⁴⁵ Third, ADR fosters flexibility, allowing parties to choose the procedure, forum, and even the mediator or arbitrator. Fourth, it often leads to better compliance with the outcome, as parties are more likely to adhere to solutions they have had a hand in shaping.⁴⁶ ADR also promotes harmony by preserving relationships, especially in disputes involving family, community, or ongoing business dealings. These

⁴¹ Mashamba J.C (2020). Guiding Notes on Mediation. <https://tanzlii.org/akn/tz/doc/booklet/2020-11-01/guiding-notes-on-mediation/eng@2020-11-01>. Accessed on 10 June 2025.

⁴² Ibid.

⁴³ Brown, H. J., & Marriott, A. L. (1999). *ADR Principles and Practice* (p. 131, 2nd ed.). Sweet & Maxwell.

⁴⁴ (Gray Born, 2022).”

⁴⁵ Mashamba, C. J. (2014). *Alternative dispute resolution in Tanzania: Law and practice* (p. 13). Mkuki na Nyota Publishers.

⁴⁶ Uwazie, E. (2011, November 30). *Alternative dispute resolution in Africa: Preventing conflict and enhancing stability*. Africa Security Brief, (16).

advantages have led to ADR being widely recognized as a vital component of modern dispute resolution systems across the world.⁴⁷

The concepts discussed above are important for understanding this study because they explain the legal, economic, and institutional context of competition in Tanzania. They help to show how disputes are managed within the Fair Competition Commission and the mechanisms, powers, and limits that influence the use of ADR. The next section presents the methodology used in this study, focusing on how dispute settlement within the FCC operates as a practical form of alternative dispute resolution.

6. METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a doctrinal research method to analyze the use of settlement as an Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) mechanism within the Fair Competition Commission (FCC) in Tanzania. It critically examined legal statutes, regulations, case law, and academic writings on competition law to interpret the framework governing competition disputes. This method allowed for an in-depth exploration of the Fair Competition Act and its Rules, highlighting gaps and limitations in the current framework, and assessing the alignment of the settlement mechanism with ADR principles, thus evaluating the effectiveness of ADR within the FCC.

The empirical method was employed to gather perspectives from key stakeholders directly involved in handling competition disputes. Structured interviews were administered to 18 respondents in Dodoma and Dar es Salaam, including FCC officers, legal practitioners specialising in competition law, business representatives involved in competition disputes, and academicians with expertise in the field. Data collected from both documentary sources and stakeholders were organized thematically, systematically coded, and categorized to identify major patterns and trends. This approach allowed the study to examine how settlement mechanisms are applied in practice, the challenges faced, and the effectiveness of these mechanisms in resolving competition disputes.

6.1 Findings

Settlement of disputes within the FCC follows procedures outlined under Rules 19(5), (6), and 21 of the Fair Competition Commission Rules.⁴⁸ Under these provisions, an applicant may request a settlement only after the Commission has issued its provisional findings. The request must be submitted to the Commissioner, either orally or in writing,

⁴⁷ Mashamba (2014) *Op Cit.*

⁴⁸ [GN. No. 344 of 2018]. Rule 21(1) states that: *A party may apply for settlement under rule 19(6) after issuance of provisional findings and but not after issuance of final findings on matter by the Commission.*

expressing the interest in engaging in settlement discussions regarding the matter under investigation. Upon receiving the application, the Commissioner determines whether to admit the request for settlement. The determination made by the Commissioner under sub-rule 2(ii) is final. If the Commissioner is satisfied with the information provided, a settlement plan is then prepared to resolve the matter within thirty days. However, if the FCC has already issued its final decision, no settlement can be initiated thereafter. The study found that, while the FCC provides for settlement as an alternative dispute resolution mechanism, the practical application of ADR is constrained by several limitations. These challenges affect the efficiency, fairness, and accessibility of settlements, as discussed in the sections below.

6.1.1 Discretionary nature of settlement within the FCC

The findings reveal that while the Fair Competition Act⁴⁹ and the FCC⁵⁰ explicitly provide for settlement, the design of this mechanism places excessive discretion in the hands of the Commission. Rule 19(6) and Rule 21 of the FCC Rules empower the Commission to “consider a settlement” once provisional findings have been issued. The study observed that the law envisions settlement as a voluntary mechanism, but it is only triggered after the Commission has established a prima facie case. Respondent from the FCC noted that, “it is after notification of provisional findings that the Commission may consider a settlement”.⁵¹ The Rules further provide that an applicant “shall submit his request... indicating his interest to engage the commissioner in a settlement discussion” and that the FCC “shall make a determination on the application for settlement.” Where such application is granted, the Commissioner prepares a settlement plan intended to conclude the matter within thirty (30) days.⁵²

This means settlement is not a right accruing automatically to the investigated party, but rather a process that depends on the Commission’s discretion. A legal practitioner interviewed remarked that “even when parties are ready to settle, it all depends on whether the Commission accepts the request. That makes settlement look like a privilege, not a right”.⁵³ This reveals how the law centralizes power in the hands of the FCC, leaving firms uncertain about whether their willingness to resolve matters amicably will ever materialize into a settlement process.

The study further found that even when the Commissioner grants permission for settlement, the process is tightly controlled by the FCC. Respondents observed that the

⁴⁹ [Cap. 285 R.E. 2023]

⁵⁰ Rules [GN. No. 344 of 2018]

⁵¹ Interview conducted with the Consumer Protection Officer, FCC Dodoma Head Office. 6th Floor, PSSSF House, Makole Road. In August 2025.

⁵² Rule 21, FCC Rules 2018).

⁵³ Interview conducted with Advocate Godfrey Chambe, from Lex Firma Attorneys at MPakani ‘B’ Kijitonyama, Dar es Salaam on September 02, 2025).

Commissioner is responsible for designing and finalizing a settlement plan, which must be completed within thirty days. This procedural design, while seemingly efficient, gives the Commission significant leverage over the terms and pace of negotiation. An officer from a business entity noted that “the Commission decides not only whether a settlement happens, but also how it happens. That does not look like real ADR, because one party controls the process”.⁵⁴ It was also observed that the discretionary model significantly affects the predictability of outcomes. Respondents explained that firms facing investigations hesitate to apply for settlement because there is no certainty that their request will be entertained. This discourages wider use of ADR within competition enforcement, as businesses prefer to either contest decision formally or wait for final determinations rather than risk rejection at the settlement stage.⁵⁵

The findings therefore reveal a fundamental weakness in the design of settlement as an ADR mechanism within the FCC. Though the statutory framework recognizes and permits settlement, the over-centralization of power in the hands of the Commission hinders its effectiveness. The process lacks autonomy and predictability as the Commission functions both as the referee and the player in determining whether disputes may be settled out of formal enforcement. Consequently, although settlement provisions signal willingness to integrate ADR into competition enforcement, their current application undermines confidence in the system and prevents settlement from operating as a genuine alternative to adjudication.

6.1.2 Lack of procedural clarity in settlements

Another critical issue revealed by this study is the absence of procedural clarity surrounding settlements within the FCC. Although the FCC Rules,⁵⁶ provides for “settlement discussions,” it does not define the specific nature of the process or the methods to be employed. Unlike formal ADR frameworks such as mediation, arbitration, or conciliation where the roles of the parties and the neutral facilitator are clearly prescribed, the FCC Rules remain silent on whether settlement is intended to mirror any of these recognized mechanisms. There are no accompanying guidelines to explain how such discussions should be conducted, what principles govern them, or what safeguards ensure fairness and neutrality. As a result, there is uncertainty as to whether settlement before the FCC is meant to function as a consensual negotiation, a facilitated mediation, or merely an administrative arrangement concluded at the discretion of the Commission.

⁵⁴ Response from Legal Officer TBL office located at Plot 79, Block 'AA', Uhuru Street, Mchikichini, Ilala, Dar es Salaam, Tanzania in August 27, 2025.

⁵⁵ Interview conducted with Advocate Godfrey Chambe, from Lex Firma Attorneys at MPakani 'B' Kijitonyama, Dar es Salaam on 2 September 2025.

⁵⁶ [GN. No. 344 of 2018].

It was observed that the rules simply refer to “settlement” without specifying whether these take the form of mediation, conciliation, or negotiation. An academic respondent observed that; “when the rules say settlement, they don’t tell us what kind of ADR this is. Is it mediation, where the Commission is a neutral facilitator, or is it negotiation, where the Commission itself bargains with the parties? The rules don’t say”⁵⁷ This ambiguity has led to inconsistencies in practice and confusion among stakeholders as to the real nature of settlement under competition law.

Respondents from within the FCC reinforced the concern over procedural uncertainty in settlement processes. They noted that the law is silent on the precise nature of settlements, offering no indication whether the process amounts to mediation, conciliation, or simple negotiation. Officials explained that, particularly in consumer protection disputes, any settlement reached is not legally binding and the FCC lacks statutory authority to enforce the outcomes. Instead, parties who fail to comply with agreed terms must seek recourse in the ordinary courts of law.⁵⁸ One FCC officer remarked that, “the law does not speak of what type of settlements these are, but I can call them negotiations because they involve discussions to settle amicably. They are not mediations because there is no mediator, nor arbitration because there is no arbitrator or any arbitral awards or means of enforcing them.”⁵⁹ This internal perspective reveals that, even from the regulator’s own vantage point, the current settlement regime lacks a defined ADR character and remains largely unenforceable.

This issue was the subject of judicial investigation in the case of *Great Wall Trading V. Chief Inspector of Merchandise Marks, FCC FCT*⁶⁰ In this case, Great Wall Trading imported electrical goods that the FCC suspected to be counterfeit under the Merchandise Marks Act. The Chief Inspector seized the goods and initiated proceedings against the company. Great Wall Trading contended that the goods were genuine and challenged the seizure. The Chief Inspector of Merchandise Marks at the FCC, acting as a mediator, conducted a mediation process and ordered Great Wall Trading to pay the mediated amount, which the plaintiff disagreed with and subsequently appealed to the Fair Competition Tribunal. The main issue before the Tribunal was whether the mediation procedure adopted by the FCC was lawful and whether the Chief Inspector had followed the required procedural steps under the Act and its regulations. The Tribunal held that the mediation procedure was unlawful, as the Merchandise Marks Act and related regulations did not provide for such a mechanism in these cases. Consequently, the Chief

⁵⁷ Response from Senior Lecturer Mzumbe University Dar Es Salaam Campus College. 12 Olympio St, DSM, Dar es Salam, in September 2025.

⁵⁸ Response from Consumer Protection Officer FCC, FCC Dodoma Head Office. 6th Floor, PSSSF House, Makole Road. 4 August 2025.

⁵⁹ Ibid.

⁶⁰ (Appeal No. 2/2009).

Inspector's decision, which had relied on the mediation, was quashed, and the Tribunal ordered that fresh proceedings be conducted in accordance with due process and the proper legal procedures.

The law is silent on whether all breaches of competition law, including serious violations such as cartels and abuse of dominance, can be settled. This ambiguity creates uncertainty for both regulators and regulated parties. The study found that some stakeholders interpret the rules as allowing settlement in virtually all cases, while others view settlement as limited to minor or procedural breaches. This lack of uniform understanding undermines the credibility of settlement as an ADR mechanism within the FCC. It was noted by the respondents that the absence of explicit guidance on eligible disputes discourages businesses from seeking settlement. A legal practitioner interviewed explained that "businesses cannot tell whether their case qualifies for settlement, because the law is not specific. You may apply and then be told your case cannot be settled."⁶¹ This highlights the practical risk of wasted effort and costs in pursuing settlement, further reducing the attractiveness of ADR. Academicians also confirmed that uncertainty on the scope of settlement weakens the predictability of competition enforcement and exposes parties to discretionary interpretations by the Commission. Therefore, unclear rules on which disputes qualify for settlement and what form of ADR it represents undermine the process's legitimacy. This ambiguity erodes stakeholder confidence and discourages businesses from viewing settlement as a real alternative. Though the law signals an intent to use ADR, the lack of detailed procedures leaves a gap that breeds uncertainty and inconsistency.

6.1.3 Limited application of ADR within the FCC

The study found that, although the Fair Competition Act⁶² and its 2018 Rules⁶³ permit settlement of disputes, the actual use of settlements has been rare. It was revealed by this study that, although the law permits settlement, practice has yet to witness settlement being done, especially when it involves prohibited practices which might attract penal punishments. Respondents noted that while settlement is theoretically optional and even serious cases could be settled, in reality, parties facing heavy penalties often resist. One legal practitioner remarked, "Even in serious cases, respondents are often reluctant to engage in settlement, fearing heavy penalties and unpredictability of outcomes."⁶⁴ In most cases, settlement within the FCC remains unsuccessful. A legal representative from

⁶¹ Response from Advocate Neema Masame, from Greenwich Law Attorneys at Hugo House 3rd Floor, Kinondoni Road Dar es Salaam. On September, 2025).

⁶² [Cap. 285 R.E. 2023].

⁶³ [GN. No. 344 of 2018].

⁶⁴ Interview conducted with Advocate Godfrey Chambe, from Lex Firma Attorneys at MPakani 'B' Kijitonyama, Dar es Salaam on September 02, 2025).

one business entity observed that, “There were several attempts to negotiate to resolve the dispute before the final decision was made. Even after the final decision was made, attempts were made through meetings to resolve the dispute (e.g., a meeting held on 10.10.2023) but were unsuccessful”.⁶⁵ Respondents from the FCC further explained that settlements often fail because parties cannot agree on the amount to be paid for breaches of competition law or because parties fail to honour settlement terms. Thus, the Commission proceeds with formal hearings.

The study further revealed the institutional setting that undermines confidence in the settlement process. Respondents explained that the FCC’s structure, acting simultaneously as investigator, adjudicator, and enforcer, creates concerns of bias and questionable impartiality. An officer from a business entity explained, “When the Commission acts as investigator and judge, it’s difficult for respondents to trust that the settlement process will be fair and impartial.”⁶⁶ Such a system discourages parties from engaging voluntarily in settlement, fearing that outcomes may be influenced by the Commission’s dual roles.

Importantly, the study found that there is no available information or official report indicating whether any disputes have actually been settled within the FCC. The FCC itself does not publish reports or data on settlements, making it impossible to verify the practical application of this ADR mechanism. This raises questions about whether the settlement process is applied at all, despite being allowed under the law. In this respect, the study found that although the law allows settlements, ADR use in the FCC is minimal. Respondents pointed to voluntary participation, concentrated authority, unclear eligibility, and other barriers as key reasons. This underuse weakens efficiency and stakeholder trust, showing that the current framework hinders an effective ADR system despite its stated intent.

6.1.4 Public interest nature of competition disputes

Another issue identified by this study concerns the limited scope of ADR in competition enforcement, which arises from the public interest nature of competition law. Unlike contractual or private disputes where the parties enjoy autonomy to negotiate settlements, competition disputes inherently involve the protection of broader market interests and consumer welfare. The FCC, being a state organ, bears responsibility to safeguard the integrity of competition in the market and prevent practices such as collusion, abuse of dominance, or unfair trade practices. For this reason, the law

⁶⁵ Interview with the Legal Officer, Tanga Cement, 2025.

⁶⁶ Response from Legal Officer TBL office located at Plot 79, Block 'AA', Uhuru Street, Mchikichini, Ilala, Dar es Salaam, Tanzania in august 27, 2025.

empowers the FCC to exercise discretionary authority in deciding whether to approve or reject settlements proposed by parties under investigation.

It was observed that this arrangement is designed to ensure that settlements are not abused by powerful firms seeking to evade liability for serious anti-competitive conduct. The study further found that, unlike processes under the Civil Procedure Code,⁶⁷ where disputing parties are entitled to ADR before proceeding to a formal hearing, competition enforcement does not accord parties such rights. Under the CPC, contractual disputes allow the parties to select a mediator of their choice or, where they fail, the court appoints a neutral mediator to assist them in reaching a compromise. This process is appropriate because the disputes arise from private contractual relations. In competition disputes, however, even when initiated by individual complainants, are carried forward by the FCC on behalf of the public interest. As such, the Commission essentially operates as the state against business entities to protect fair competition and consumers, making the process fundamentally different from private dispute settlement.⁶⁸

Respondents from within the FCC observed that, “Competition enforcement cannot be left entirely in the hands of disputing parties, as the consequences of anti-competitive conduct extend far beyond their private interests. The discretion of the Commission is vital to prevent abuse and to ensure settlements do not undermine market integrity.”⁶⁹ Likewise, an academician emphasized the contractual nature of ADR and questioned its applicability to competition disputes, noting, “ADR mechanisms work well where parties have contractual relations, but in competition disputes the parties are not equals in a contract; it is the state acting in the public interest against firms alleged to distort the market”.⁷⁰ In this point of view, the limitation of ADR in competition enforcement highlights a tension between efficiency in dispute resolution and the need to maintain robust oversight in the protection of fair competition and consumer welfare. Although respondents acknowledged the importance of safeguarding the integrity of proceedings, they also questioned the absence of clarity in the FCC’s handling of settlements. Notably, no reports or publicly available information indicate whether any disputes have ever been resolved through ADR within the Commission. This silence raises concerns over the actual application of settlement, even though it is inadequately allowed by law.

⁶⁷ [Cap. 33 R.E. 2023].

⁶⁸ Response from Senior Lecturer Mzumbe University Dar Es Salaam Campus College. 12 Olympio St, DSM, Dar es Salam, in September 2025.

⁶⁹ Director for Restrictive Trade Practices FCC, FCC Dodoma Head Office. 6th Floor, PSSF House, Makole Road. In August 2025.

⁷⁰ Response from Senior Law Lecturer UDSM Mwalimu Julius Nyerere Mlimani Campus, P.O. Box 35091, Dar es Salaam, Tanzania, September, 2025.

7. CONCLUSION

The study found that although the Fair Competition Commission formally allows settlement as an alternative dispute resolution mechanism, its practical use is severely limited. The process is highly discretionary, giving the Commission significant control, which makes settlement seem more like a privilege than a right. There is also a lack of clarity in the rules, as they do not specify how settlements should be conducted, what principles should guide them, or what safeguards exist to ensure fairness. As a result, settlements are rare, with parties often preferring formal hearings due to uncertainty about outcomes and concerns over the Commission's dual role as investigator and adjudicator. Furthermore, the public interest nature of competition disputes restricts the scope of ADR, as the Commission must protect market integrity and consumer welfare, not just the interests of the parties involved. Generally, while the law provides for settlement and shows an intent to integrate ADR into competition enforcement, the current design and practice undermine its effectiveness, reducing autonomy, predictability, and stakeholder confidence, and limiting the credibility of settlement as a real alternative to formal adjudication. The next section presents recommendations to strengthen the settlement process within the FCC to make it more efficient, fair, and accessible.

To strengthen the effectiveness of ADR within the FCC, several measures are recommended. First, the Fair Competition Act and the FCC Rules should be amended to provide clearer statutory authority for ADR processes. Such amendments must explicitly define settlement and other ADR mechanisms, clarify the Commission's discretionary powers while ensuring that parties have clear rights to initiate ADR, and specify which disputes are eligible for settlement. Second, the FCC should develop comprehensive ADR Guidelines to operationalize settlements. These guidelines should outline the types of ADR available, detail the roles of parties and the Commission, provide step-by-step procedures, and include safeguards to ensure fairness, impartiality, transparency, and confidentiality. Third, transparency should be enhanced through mandatory reporting and publication of ADR outcomes. Even anonymized summaries would build public trust, demonstrate accountability, and provide empirical data to evaluate ADR's effectiveness within the competition law framework. Finally, deliberate efforts should be made to build capacity and awareness among FCC staff, legal practitioners, and market participants. Training programs, workshops, and awareness campaigns would equip stakeholders with the necessary knowledge and skills to effectively engage in ADR, encourage early resolution of disputes, and foster confidence in the FCC's enforcement mechanisms.

In conclusion, while the law provides for settlements and signals an intent to integrate ADR into competition enforcement, the current design and practice undermine its effectiveness. By reforming the statutory framework, developing guidelines, ensuring

transparency, and strengthening institutional capacity, settlement can evolve into a credible and effective alternative to formal adjudication in Tanzania's competition law regime.